

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the eighth regular issue in 2017 with one high quality regular paper and five papers from the focused topic "*Big data in Cross-Disciplinary Research*".

As always, I'd like to thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. I'd particularly like to acknowledge the generous support of the members of the J.UCS consortium which enables us to continue to offer J.UCS as an open content journal without publication fees.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce one accepted paper in a research collaboration form two different countries, Sweden and Republic of South Africa. Johanna Björklund, Loek Cleophas and My Karlsson evaluated in their paper probabilistic lexicalized tree-insertion grammars on a classification task relevant for automatic speech recognition.

The editors of the focused topic, Giangiacomo Bravo from the Linnaeus University, Sweden, Mikko Laitinen from the Linnaeus University, Sweden and the University of Eastern Finland and Magnus Levin, Welf Löwe and Göran Petersson from the Linnaeus University, Sweden, write:

“The ubiquity of sensor, computing, communication, and storage technologies provides us with access to previously unknown amounts of data - Big Data. Big Data has revolutionized research communities and their scientific methodologies. It has, for instance, innovated the approaches to knowledge and theory building, validation, and exploitation taken in the engineering sciences. The humanities and social sciences even face a paradigm shift away from data-scarce, static, coarse-grained and simple studies towards data-rich, dynamic, high resolution, and complex observations and simulations. The present focused topic presents investigations from different research fields in which the focus is either on utilizing Big Data or charting the benefits of using such evidence in basic research.

The paper “Big Data in Cross-Disciplinary Research” by Giangiacomo Bravo, Mikko Laitinen, Magnus Levin, Welf Löwe, and Göran Petersson summarizes the observations of the guest editors of this focused topic on how the use of Big Data in research has matured over the last years.

The paper “Utilizing Multilingual Language Data in (Nearly) Real time: the Case of the Nordic Tweet Stream” by Mikko Laitinen, Jonas Lundberg, Magnus Levin, and Alexander Lakaw presents a digital humanities project that downloads Twitter messages and two case studies illustrating how this corpus could be used as empirical evidence in studies focusing on the global spread of English.

The paper “Prospects and Challenges for the Computational Social Sciences” by Giangiacomo Bravo and Mike Farjam illustrates the developments of computational

social sciences since the term was coined in 2009 and (re-) assesses its potentialities and risks.

The paper “Digitalization Canvas – Towards Identifying Digitalization Use Cases and Projects” by Andreas Heberle, Welf Löwe, Anders Gustafsson, and Örjan Vorrei describes an industry project where digitalization use cases have been identified, evaluated, and prioritized with respect to benefits and costs leading to a portfolio of projects, some with quick and easy wins and some others with mid- to long-term benefits.

The paper “(Big) Data in Library and Information Science: A Brief Overview of Some Important Problem Areas” by Koraljka Golub and Joacim Hansson argues for the need to find new ways of organizing documentation, information and data, and to develop instruments for research evaluation in a world where the differences between formal publications, other forms of communication and data sharing are becoming weaker.”

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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